

Challenges and Benefits of Open Sourcing Mission Software from the Beginning

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In Planetary Science, each mission is unique

Unique Goals

Unique Hardware

Unique People

Unique Software

Most of the mission science software is
releasable.

ITAR / EAR
or otherwise
restricted

Historically it has not been released.

SPD-41a is meant to change this.

- Focuses on good outcomes
- Does not provide a lot of guidance

Historical Pattern

- Begin writing science software
- Operate Mission, continue writing software
- Write papers, archive data, continue writing software
- Figure out if we can release any of this science software

Modern Mission not bound by SPD-41a

Project Scientist or PI

Lead A

Lead B

Lead C

All missions need guidance
on how to successfully plan
to release software

Born Open

- Inverts typical pattern of: write code, then make open.
- Instead: decide that code should be open, and then write open code.

For Successful Mission Software Release

Have a good Open Source Plan before any new software is written.

Establish separate repositories for open and closed code.

Before any piece of software is written: determine its “openness.” If it can be open, it should be “born open” and developed in an open repo.